

PROCESSING OF IN SITU COMPOSITES BASED ON THERMOPLASTIC MATRICES AND LIQUID CRYSTALLINE POLYMERS

H. H. Chen, J. P. de Souza, D. G. Baird,
K. T. Teh*, and J. Morton*

Department of Chemical Engineering and
*Department of Engineering Science and Mechanics
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg, VA 24061

ABSTRACT

One of the major problems in the use of thermoplastic composites is the melting of the fibers with the matrix. In our laboratory, we have developed a process for generating the reinforcement using liquid crystalline polymers within the matrix. The idea of reinforcing thermoplastic matrices with liquid crystalline polymers (LCPs), which are known to form high modulus and strength fibers, on an in situ basis is a relatively new concept. This paper is concerned with a new approach to generating continuous LCP fibrils within thermoplastic matrices using a novel mixing process. The strands of reinforced thermoplastic possess exceptionally high physical properties and more resemble those long fiber composites. The strands can be further processed by various methods such as injection molding, compression molding, and thermoforming. The properties of strands and injection molded parts are compared with those of glass reinforced thermoplastics. The effect of compatibilization on the properties, surface finish, and morphology are also discussed.

(Keywords: thermoplastic, liquid crystalline polymers, in situ composites, compatibilization, and morphology)

INTRODUCTION

Polymer blends comprised of a thermoplastic matrix reinforced with liquid crystalline polymers (LCPs) have been an area of considerable interest to researchers in the past several years (1-9). Under certain processing conditions, LCPs can develop a fibrillar morphology with a high degree of orientation leading to enhanced mechanical properties of the blends. Because the reinforcement is generated during melt processing, these blends are sometimes referred to as in situ composites.

Reinforcement of Polypropylene with several LCPs has been attempted in our laboratory(10,11) and by other researchers(12,13). Although the blends exhibited improvements in modulus, they tend to show no improvements in tensile strength compared to that of pure PP. The PP/LCP blends have poor surface appearance and poor adhesion between PP and the LCPs. Besides, the LCP phase shows poor dispersion indicating the incompatibility of the blends.

Compatibilization has been known to overcome the problems of poor dispersion and poor adhesion in blends of incompatible polymers(14). Compatibilizers are usually block or graft copolymers which possess similar structures in both ends to those polymers being blended. The compatibilizer acts as a polymeric surfactant and reduces the interfacial tension, and improves adhesion between the matrix and dispersed phase which results in better mechanical properties of the incompatible polymer blends(14,15). Our previous attempts to compatibilize PP/LCP blends resulted in significant enhancements in tensile strength, modulus, and surface appearance over those of uncompatibilized blends(11). The improvements in properties of these blends were attributed to better adhesion and dispersion in the blends.

LCPs usually have higher melting points, and thus, they are processed at relatively higher temperatures than commodity thermoplastics, such as polypropylene (PP) and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). A novel mixing technique, called dual-extruder mixing process, has been developed

in our laboratory in which two polymers with non-overlapping processing temperatures can be melt blended (16,17). By using this technique, we have successfully made PP and PET composites with the LCP reinforcements.

Strands made by this method possess higher physical properties and more resemble those of long fiber composites and can be further processed by various methods such as injection molding, compression molding, and thermoforming.

In this study, strands of PP based in situ composites with one LCP are produced using this novel mixing technique. The properties of strands and injection molded parts are discussed. The effects of processing conditions and compatibilization on the properties and morphology of PP based in situ composites are also discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

The LCP used in this study was Vectra B950 (Hoechst Celanese) and is believed to be a wholly aromatic liquid crystal polyesteramide composed of 58 mol % 2-hydroxy-6-naphthoic acid (HNA), 21 mol % terephthalic acid (TPA) and 21 mol % 4-hydroxy acetanilide. Although various matrices can be used, results we reported for polypropylene, PP (Pro-Fax 6823), a commodity thermoplastic purchased from HIMONT. The compatibilizer is a maleic anhydride grafted PP copolymer (MA). Before processing, LCP pellets were dried in a convection oven at 115°C for at least 24 hours and the compatibilizer was dried in a vacuum oven at 95-100°C overnight.

BLENDING PROCESS

Details of the blending process are explained with reference to the schematic of the apparatus shown in Figure 1. The matrix material and the reinforcing LCP were plasticated separately in the two extruders (Killion-KL100, 1" diameter). The maximum barrel temperatures during this separate plastication step were as follows: LCP extruder- 290°C and PP extruder-240°C. The melt streams were then joined and blended in a Kenics static mixer with 15 helical mixing elements. A capillary die with a diameter of 0.125" and an L/D ratio of 10 was adapted to the exit of the static mixer to make the strands. The temperatures of the static mixer was maintained at between 215-225°C. The composition of the blends was determined by the feeding rate of each extruder. The extrudate was then taken up between a pair of chill rolls whose speed could be varied to obtain different draw ratios. An icewater bath was used to quench the extrudate immediately downstream of the capillary die before drawing. Two different draw ratios, based on cross sectional areas of die and extrudate, were obtained for most blends. The strands were then pelletized for injection molding.

Figure 1. Schematic of Dual Extruder Mixing System.

INJECTION MOLDING

Rectangular plaques of PP/Vectra B blends with and without compatibilizer were injection molded using an Arburg Injection Molder (Model 222-55-20). Two different processing conditions were used. One was set at PP processing conditions in order not to melt the preregenerated LCP fibrils and the maximum barrel temperature was set at 230°C. In the other set of processing conditions the barrel temperature was set above the melting point of the LCP (T_m of Vectra B is 280°C). The mold was kept at room temperature for both processing conditions.

MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The tensile modulus and strength of the blend strands and injection molded plaques were measured using an Instron Mechanical Tester (Model 4204). For strands, the cross head speed was 1.0 mm/min. and the gage length was 14 cm/min. The test samples were strips of approximate dimensions of 80 or 75 mm in length and 12.5 mm in width cut from plaques. The cross head speed was 1.27 mm/min.. The strain was measured using an extensometer (Instron Model 2630-25). The arithmetic average and the standard deviation of the tensile properties were calculated using a minimum of four samples.

The flexural modulus and strength of the plaques were measured using an Instron Mechanical Tester (Model 4204) with a three point bending fixture. The test samples cut from plaques were strips of approximate dimensions of 80 or 75 mm in length and 12.5 mm in width. The cross head speed was 2.80 mm/min. with a span to depth ratio of 32. The arithmetic average and the standard deviation of the tensile properties were calculated using a minimum of four samples.

MORPHOLOGICAL STUDIES

The morphology was determined by means of a scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Cambridge StereoscanS200) with an accelerating voltage of 25kV. The samples were fractured after immersing them in liquid nitrogen for five minutes. The fractured samples were then placed on aluminum stubs and sputter-coated with gold using a Bio-Rad sputter coater.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The theory and reasoning behind the development of the dual- extruder mixing method which favors the generation of continuous LCP fibrils within the matrix polymer have been discussed elsewhere (16,18), and they will not be discussed here. It is believed that the viscosity ratio (dispersed LCP phase to matrix phase) must be lower than or equal to unity for the dispersed phase to be successfully elongated from droplets into highly elongated fibrils. However, the dual mixer technique allows one to overcome this restriction.

Strands of PP/Vectra B blends with and without compatibilization were extruded using the dual-extruder mixing method. Two draw ratios were produced for each blend. The effect of draw ratio on tensile properties of PP/Vectra B blend strands will be discussed. The strands were then pelletized and processed by standard polymer processing method such as injection molding at temperatures below and above the melting point of Vectra B. The effect of processing conditions on the tensile properties and morphology of the composites is discussed next.

In Table 1 are shown the tensile properties of strands of PP/Vectra B (83/17) blends with and without compatibilizer. From this table, one can see that the tensile strength and modulus of uncompatibilized blends increased with the increase of the draw ratio. The tensile strength increased from 47.5 to 110.6 MPa with the increase of draw ratio from 5.13 to 17.1 and the modulus increased from 2.91 to 10.0 GPa. Similar results are also observed for the compatibilized PP/Vectra B blend strands. The tensile strength increased from 94.2 MPa to 102.2 MPa with the increase of draw ratio from 7.08 to 15.3 and the modulus increased from 7.32 to 10.8 GPa. The reason for this improvement is due to the highly oriented and finer LCP fibrils in the blends with the increase of the draw ratio. Additionally, the strands with higher draw ratio, exhibit LCP fibrils which appear to be larger in number and of higher aspect ratio than those with lower draw. Thus

Table 1. Tensile Properties of PP/Vectra B Blend Strands

Materials	Draw Ratio	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Modulus (GPa)
PP/Vectra B 83/17	5.13	47.15 (3.70)	2.910 (0.45)
	17.1	110.6 (14.2)	10.03 (1.10)
PP(MA)/Vectra B 83(10)/17	7.08	94.20 (13.7)	7.323 (0.57)
	15.3	102.2 (12.0)	10.78 (0.93)

MA : Compatibilizer, Strain Rate : 1.0 mm/min. Gage Length : 14 cm, Mixer with 15 elements, Standard deviations are given in the parenthesis.

they tend to further enhance the properties of the in situ composites (18). Strands with higher draw ratios have been obtained with a larger diameter capillary die. The tensile properties of the strands tend to level off with the increase of the draw ratio especially the modulus of the strands. However, the tensile properties of the compatibilized blends are better than those of the uncompatibilized blends. The enhanced strength and modulus suggest possibly that better adhesion between PP and Vectra B exists. It is believed that the compatibilization occurs during the reactive extrusion process, which brings PP grafting with Vectra B and this improves their mutual compatibility and the adhesion between PP and Vectra B (19).

Fracture surfaces of compatibilized PP/Vectra B strands were examined by means of SEM to ascertain the morphology. Figure 2 shows the fracture surface of compatibilized PP/Vectra B blend strand with a draw ratio of 15.3. The micrograph shows that long LCP fibrils appear to orient in the draw direction and are dispersed uniformly in the blends with no visible skin-core structure. The presence of these highly oriented LCP fibrils is responsible for the enhancement of properties of the blends.

Injection molded plaques were made from these strands by processing at two different conditions. The first processing conditions were set at PP temperatures and the maximum temperature was set at 230°C, i.e. the Vectra B was not melted. The second set of processing conditions was also set at PP temperatures except one zone temperature was set at 290°C which is slightly higher than the melting point of Vectra B. The tensile properties of injection molded plaques made from PP/Vectra B strands are shown in Table 2.

There are significant improvements in the tensile strengths and moduli of the compatibilized PP/Vectra B blends over those blends which were not compatibilized. The tensile strength in the machine direction increased from 26 MPa to 36 MPa with compatibilization for strands produced at similar draw ratio, and also the tensile strength increased from 20.2 MPa to 27.7 MPa in the transverse direction. The moduli of compatibilized PP/Vectra B blends increased slightly in both the machine and transverse directions. The elongation at yield decreased slightly in both directions with compatibilization. The enhanced improvements in tensile strengths and moduli of compatibilized PP/Vectra B blends are attributed to better adhesion between PP and Vectra B. The plaques made with compatibilized PP/Vectra B strands have a better surface finish, which is not shown in this report, and a lower degree of anisotropy than those made with uncompatibilized strands. It was also found that the draw ratio of the strands does not enhance much on tensile properties of compatibilized PP/Vectra B blend plaques in both the machine and transverse directions.

When the processing conditions were changed during injection molding, i.e. one temperature zone was set at 290°C, which is above the melting point of Vectra B, the tensile strengths increased slightly in the machine direction, and the moduli decreased in the transverse direction for both compatibilized and uncompatibilized blends. The degree of anisotropy increased for the samples produced using the higher temperatures. The reason can probably be attributed to the different

Figure 2. SEM Micrograph of Compatibilized PP/Vectra B (83/17) Strand, 15 Mixer Elements and Draw Ratio of 15.3.

Table 2. Tensile Properties of PP/Vectra B Blend Plaques

Materials	Tensile Strength (MPa)		Modulus (GPa)		Elongation (%)	
	M. D.	T. D.	M. D.	T. D.	M. D.	T. D.
PP/VB 83/17 (D.R. = 17.1)	26.0 (1.54)	20.2 (1.47)	2.40 (0.55)	1.98 (0.18)	4.20 (1.27)	2.89 (0.88)
PP/VB* 83/17 (D.R. = 17.1)	28.0 (2.50)	17.5 (1.07)	3.63 (0.44)	1.83 (0.40)	1.41 (0.23)	1.77 (0.45)
PP(MA)/VB 83(10)/17 (D.R. = 7.08)	35.9 (1.58)	28.9 (0.62)	2.59 (0.18)	2.46 (0.17)	3.35 (0.42)	2.41 (0.11)
PP(MA)/VB 83(10)/17 (D.R. = 15.3)	35.1 (1.80)	27.7 (0.38)	2.61 (0.17)	2.37 (0.26)	4.21 (0.38)	2.40 (0.20)
PP(MA)/VB* 83(10)/17 (D.R. = 15.3)	38.8 (4.05)	28.6 (1.39)	2.64 (0.42)	1.99 (0.13)	2.52 (0.35)	3.12 (0.10)

M.D. : Machine Direction, T. D. : Transverse Direction, MA : Compatibilizer, Static Mixer with 15 elements, * : One zone temperature was set at 290°C, Standard Deviations are given in the parenthesis.

mold filling mechanisms. With one temperature zone is set above the melting point of Vectra B, the pregenerated LCP fibrils remelt during injection molding. During mold filling the deformations at the advancing front lead to the formation of LCP fibrils (20). Evidence is shown in the SEM micrographs in Fig. 3(a) for compatibilized PP/Vectra B blends. A partial skin/core structure is observed in this micrograph. In the skin region, the LCP fibrils are more oriented in the flow direction while in the core region they are oriented perpendicular to the flow direction. The enhancement of tensile strength in the machine direction is attributed to the oriented LCP fibrils in the skin region for compatibilized PP/Vectra B blends.

On the contrary, there is no evidence of a skin/core structure in compatibilized PP/Vectra B blends, when the temperatures are kept below the melting point of the LCP. This is seen in the micrograph of Fig. 3(b). In this micrograph, the pregenerated LCP fibrils are more randomly oriented in the flow direction. The process temperature does not deform LCP fibrils during injection molding. The randomly oriented LCP fibrils favor the balance of properties in both directions especially the modulus of the blends. Thus there is a reduction in the anisotropy of PP/Vectra B blends in most instances.

Similar results are observed in the flexural properties of injection molded plaques made from PP/Vectra B strands as shown in Table 3. Generally, compatibilization and processing conditions play important roles in affecting the flexural properties of PP/Vectra B blends. For compatibilized blends, the flexural strength increased 20% in both machine and transverse directions and the modulus increased 15% in both directions compared with uncompatibilized blends. The enhanced flexural strength and modulus of PP/Vectra B blends are due to better adhesion between PP and Vectra B with compatibilization. The compatibilization occurs during the reactive extrusion process which brings PP grafting with Vectra B and improves the compatibility and adhesion between the two polymers.

Table 3. Flexural Properties of PP/Vectra B Blends

Materials	Flexural Strength (MPa)		Modulus (GPa)	
	M. D.	T. D.	M. D.	T. D.
PP/VB 83/17 (D.R. = 17.1)	50.7 (4.46)	48.0 (0.37)	3.11 (0.11)	2.56 (0.06)
PP/VB* 83/17 (D.R. = 17.1)	53.1 (4.04)	44.1 (4.63)	4.89 (0.44)	2.91 (0.52)
PP(MA)/VB 83(10)/17 (D.R. = 7.08)	60.2 (2.83)	61.0 (1.14)	3.72 (0.23)	3.01 (0.04)
PP(MA)/VB 83(10)/17 (D.R. = 15.3)	62.9 (3.14)	58.3 (2.47)	3.57 (0.25)	3.10 (0.23)
PP(MA)/VB* 83(10)/17 (D.R. = 15.3)	69.4 (2.76)	53.6 (3.06)	4.41 (0.23)	3.03 (0.23)

MA : Compatibilizer, D. R. : Draw Ratio, Strain Rate : 2.8 mm/min., Span-Depth Ratio : 32, * : One zone temperature was set at 290°C, Static Mixer with 15 elements, Standard Deviations are given in the parenthesis.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3. SEM Micrographs of Compatibilized PP/Vectra B (83/17) Plaques Surfaces Fractured along the Machine Direction and Processed at Different Conditions, (a) One zone set at 290°C, (b) PP Processing Conditions, $T_{\max} = 230^{\circ}\text{C}$, 15 Mixer Elements and Draw Ratio of 15.3.

Flexural strength and modulus are also improved in both directions with the change of processing conditions during injection molding, but the degree of anisotropy of the blends increased slightly. The reason for these improvements is also attributed to a skin layer of the LCP fibrils.

CONCLUSIONS

Continuous LCP fibrils within the polypropylene matrix have been generated using the dual-extruder mixing process. Strands of PP/Vectra B possess exceptionally high physical properties, and the properties more resemble those of long fiber composites.

The tensile strength and modulus of PP/Vectra B strands increased with the increase of the draw ratio. Highly oriented and uniformly dispersed LCP fibrils are observed in strands with a higher draw ratio. Compatibilization improved physical properties of these strands. The enhanced tensile strength and modulus of the strands are attributed to better adhesion between PP and Vectra B.

Compatibilization and processing conditions have a great effect on tensile and flexural properties of injection molded plaques made from PP/Vectra B strands. The enhancement in properties and surface finish are mainly due to improved adhesion between PP and Vectra B and a finer and more uniform distribution of the LCP phase brought about by compatibilization. Processing conditions have a great effect on the anisotropy of the blends. The degree of anisotropy decreased in most compatibilized blends and increased with the increase of processing temperatures.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We gratefully acknowledge support of this work from the Army Research Office, Grant No. DAA L03-91-G-0166 and the National Science Foundation Center For High Performance Adhesives and Composites, Grant No.DMR-9120004.

REFERENCES

1. Crevecoeur, G. and Groeninckx, G., Polym. Eng. Sci., 30(9), 532 (1990)
2. Isayev, A. I. and Modic, M., Polym. Comp., 8(3), 158 (1987).
3. Weiss, R. A., Huh, W. and Nicolais, L., Polym. Eng. Sci., 27(9), 684 (1987).
4. Subramanian, P. R. and Isayev, A. I., SPE Tech. Pap. (ANTEC 90), 48, 489 (1990).
5. Weiss, R. A., Chung, N. S. and Dutta, D., ACS Polymer Preprints, 30(2), 544 (1989).
6. Kiss, G., Polym. Eng. Sci., 27, 410 (1987).
7. Bassett, B. R. and Yee, A. F., Polym. Compos., 11(1), 10 (1990).
8. Sukhadia, A. M., Done, D. and Baird, D. G., Polym. Eng. Sci., 30(9), 519 (1990).
9. Sun, T., Baird, D. G., Huang, H. H., Done, D. S. and Wilkes, G. L., Conference of the American Society for Composite Materials Proc., 4 (1989).
10. Done, D., Sukhadia, A., Datta, A. and Baird, D. G., SPE Tech Pap. (ANTEC 90), 48, 1857 (1990).
11. Datta, A., Sukhadia, A. M., de Souza, J. P. and Baird, D. G. SPE Tech. Pap., 49, 1857 (1991).
12. European Patent 0 340 655 A2, (Nov. 8, 1989), Federici, C. Attalla, G. and Chapoy, L..
13. Seppala, J., Heino, M. and Kapanen, C., J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 44, 1051 (1992).
14. Gaylord, N. G., J. Macromol. Sci. (Chem.), A26, 8, 1211 (1989).
15. Dagli, S. S., Xanthos, M. and Bisenberger, J. A., SPE Tech. Pap. (ANTEC 90), 48, 1924 (1990).
16. Sukhadia, A. M., Datta, A. and Baird, D. G., Conf. Proc. SAMPE (1991).
17. Pending U.S. Patent application, 'Mixing Process For Generating In Situ Reinforced Thermoplastics', Baird, D. G. and Sukhadia, A. M., Virginia Tech, 1990.
18. Sukhadia, A. M., Ph. D. Dissertation, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University, 1991.
19. Pending U.S. Patent application, 'Compatible blends of Polypropylene and a liquid crystalline polymer', Baird, D. G. and Datta, A., Virginia Tech, (April, 1990).
20. Baird, D. G. and Wilkes, G. L., Polym. Eng. and Sci. Mid-August, Vol. 23, 11, 632 (1983).